

Table S1. Biochemical characteristics of the studied strains

Characteristic	Strain		
	ASD3451	ASD5720 ^T	ASD4241 ^T
Indole production	-	-	-
Urease activity	-	-	-
Acid production from D- <u>glucose</u>	+	+	+
Acid production from D- <u>mannitol</u>	+	+	+
Acid production from <u>lactose</u>	+	+	-
Acid production from <u>sucrose</u>	-	-	-
Acid production from <u>maltose</u>	Weak	Weak	-
Acid production from <u>salicin</u>	-	-	-
Acid production from D- <u>xylose</u>	+	+	+
Acid production from L- <u>arabinose</u>	+	+	+
Gelatin digestion	-	-	-
Aesculin hydrolysis	-	-	-
Acid production from <u>glycerol</u>	-	-	-
Acid production from D- <u>cellobiose</u>	-	-	-
Acid production from <u>mannose</u>	+	+	+
Acid production from D- <u>melezitose</u>	-	-	-
Acid production from D- <u>raffinose</u>	+	+	-
Acid production from D- <u>sorbitol</u>	+	+	Growth stimulation
Acid production from L- <u>rhamnose</u>	+	+	+
Acid production from D- <u>trehalose</u>	-	-	-
Acid production from <u>starch</u>	-	-	+
Catalase production	-	-	-